

Modulation Synthesis in Digital and Analogue Computing Environments

Victor Lazzarini and Joseph Timoney¹

¹Maynooth University
Maynooth, Ireland

{victor.lazzarini, joseph.timoney}@mu.ie

Abstract. *This paper surveys the area of modulation synthesis for digital and analogue computing applications. We explore the key definitions, classic methods, and some more recent developments. The key points for digital and analogue implementations are discussed, with examples in the form of diagrams. Modulation synthesis is shown to be an important resource for ubiquitous music composition and performance.*

Modulation synthesis is a class of techniques that employ the combination of a few simple waveforms (often sinusoidal) in order to produce complex spectra with dynamic characteristics. Among these, we find several methods, some of these based on various forms of amplitude modulation (AM), and others based on frequency or phase modulation (FM/PM) of signals. This survey paper aims to provide an overview of such techniques, focusing particularly on the non-linear distortion-based techniques of FM and PM and their extended forms. These may find important applications in various ubiquitous contexts, both in the context of digital environments (e.g., microprocessor-based embedded systems, music programming languages) and in analogue music computing (modular systems, DIY electronics, etc., as outlined in [Lazzarini and Timoney 2020]). The text is mostly non-mathematical, but a complete theoretical treatment of these methods can be found in [Lazzarini 2021].

1. Modulation

It is possible to describe all forms of modulation synthesis as variations of a basic arrangement consisting of the product of two signals [Bloch 1944]. We can represent modulation synthesis in this way as the action of a modulator on a carrier, through some means of amplification, which effects a multiplication operation (real or complex). This is defined in a very simple signal flowchart, shown in Fig. 1, where the triangle symbol stands for a black box product operator. In simple forms of modulation synthesis, the carrier takes the form of a real sinusoid, but this restriction is not imposed more generally. The modulator signal, on the other hand will depend on the type of modulation that is employed.

Figure 1. Modulation Synthesis as the product of carrier and modulator signals

The simplest configuration employs a sinusoidal wave, and the result is called *sinusoidal ring modulation*. This is in fact a specific instance of a more general method

of amplitude modulation. The resulting spectrum, in the case of a sinusoidal carrier, is composed of the sum and difference of the carrier and the modulator frequencies. On the other hand, if we employ analytic signals for both carrier and modulator, it is possible to produce single-sided spectra. These will contain either the sums or the differences of the carrier and modulator frequencies. For this to be implemented, real-valued input signals need to be placed in quadrature before complex multiplication is applied. In the case of sinusoids, this means employing complex sinusoids as carrier and/or modulators. A typical application of the single-sideband is in the frequency shifter effect, where the frequencies of an input signal are shifted upwards or downwards by a complex sinusoidal modulator.

1.1. Phase Modulation

In PM, the modulation signal that is applied to a sinusoidal carrier is put first through a *waveshaper*. This is a very important element of a synthesis system: it allows an input signal to be mapped by a given function, producing a non-linear modification of that signal. In its simplest form, we can describe the output of an oscillator as a waveshaper acting on a linear phase function, producing a waveform that is defined by a particular waveshaping function. Figure 2 (left) shows such a representation of a cosine wave oscillator, as a waveshaper mapping an input phase. Normally such a signal is a periodically-repeating ramp defined within a certain range (e.g. 0 to 2π in the case of the cosine wave oscillator example), but can also be obtained by direct integration of a frequency input¹. Waveshapers may be constructed for various other periodic functions, and in general we can describe it as an arbitrary function $f(x)$ defined over a given range of inputs. In the case of PM, the modulation signal in the Fig 1 flowchart is taken from a complex-valued sinusoidal *waveshaper*, as shown in Fig. 2 (middle). The input to this waveshaper can be any signal, but in simple PM we use a sinusoid. So, in this case, the waveshaper signal is in fact a mapping of a sinusoid by a complex sinusoid. If we take the carrier signal to be again analytic, in its simplest form another complex sinusoid, then the result of the complex product of the two signals is equivalent to the modulation of the phase of the carrier signal. In practice, we can avoid the complex multiplication since we want a result that is real-valued, by rearranging the operations (Fig. 2, right). Furthermore, this also means we can also apply the input signal directly to offset the phase of the carrier signal. For this, of course, we need to have the means of such fine control over the carrier phase. If this signal is a sinusoid, all we need to do is compute its phase as the sum of the phase and modulator. This can also be represented by a waveshaping expression, where the input is the modulator input offset by a linear phase function, and the waveshaper is a sinusoid. This is the form that is usually implemented in most cases. However, the form given above using the general modulation synthesis flowchart is important because it can lead to interesting variations of the PM synthesis method. From the generalised modulation description of PM we can derive the resulting synthesis spectrum. As we have noted, the ring modulation of a sinusoid and an arbitrary waveform with many harmonics produces the sums and differences between the sinusoid and the frequencies of each partial. In the case of PM, the output of the waveshaper, the modulation signal, is a waveform with a well-defined spectrum composed of several harmonics of the modulation frequency f_m , including a DC term at 0Hz. Therefore the carrier-modulated output will be composed of frequencies at $f_c \pm n f_m$, for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. There are actually an infinite number of components, but since the higher harmonics of the modulation signal have little energy,

we can consider only a certain number of them to be significant. In simple PM, where we have a sinusoidal modulation source, the number of significant sideband partials is directly related to the peak amplitude of the modulator. We call this parameter the *index of modulation* z . We can estimate the bandwidth of the signal according to it: the upper sideband will extend to $f_c + kf_m$ for $k \approx 4z$ [Corrington 1947], beyond which any signal components have very little audible significance. In any case, we can use the index of modulation as a direct means of controlling the spectral distribution in a PM waveform. The relationship between f_c and f_m is also significant. Chowning ([Chowning 1973]) made an interesting analysis of the ratio of these two frequencies and came to a number of general conclusions, which are very useful in sound design. He noted that If the ratio $f_c : f_m$ can be put into a fraction of two small integers, $a : b$, then resulting spectrum will be perceived to be harmonic, with fundamental frequency set to $\frac{f_c}{a}$ or $\frac{f_m}{b}$. If $b > 1$, then all harmonics that are integer multiples of b will be missing from the spectrum. On the other hand, if the ratio cannot be put into such a fraction, or if a fraction of larger integers results, then the spectrum will be perceived to be inharmonic, with no defined fundamental frequency.

Figure 2. Cosine oscillator (left), phase modulation using a complex exponential waveshaper (middle), and phase modulation using a cosine wave carrier (right)

1.2. Frequency Modulation

Frequency Modulation is often confused with PM. While there are many similarities and in general we may state one in terms of the other, they are actually distinct methods with different implementations. Using the general modulation synthesis model, FM employs an integration step prior to the waveshaping step, which is normally built into a unit called the *oscillator*. The integrator actually makes the frequency modulation signal into a phase modulation input. Following it, the two techniques are identical and can be treated using the same theoretical tools. However, we should not neglect that there is an integration involved, because there are important consequences that follow from it. As with PM, the usual implementation of FM is more direct: we apply the signal to modify (additively) the frequency of an oscillator. For this to be implemented, the oscillator takes a variable frequency as input, which may be positive or negative. We can describe such a unit using a flowchart where it produces an arbitrary periodic waveform, whose frequency is offset by a modulation signal. The significance of these differences will play out when the methods are deployed in either digital or analogue computing environments, and also if we attempt to expand FM or PM beyond their simple forms. For now, it is important to note that the integration step through which the modulation signal is put in FM will cause a phase delay, which in some situations can be significant. Another important consideration is how to

determine the peak amplitude of the modulation signal to obtain a given spectrum. Due to the integration, the index of modulation needs to be scaled by the modulation frequency to define the modulator amplitude. This is sometimes defined as a frequency deviation value, which gives the minimum and maximum values of the instantaneous frequency of the carrier. In any case, to determine exactly the output spectrum, it is always needed to take the integration into account and put FM in terms of PM, as the theory has been built around the latter, not the former. Figure 3 shows flowcharts for simple PM and FM side-by-side, which are designed to be equivalent in terms of output waveforms. Note that in order to having matching spectra, the modulator phases are offset by $\pi/2$, and their amplitudes differ by an f_m factor, due to the phase shift introduced by integration.

Figure 3. Simple PM (left) and FM (right) synthesis flowcharts

2. Digital Computing Environments

While FM was possible in analogue contexts prior to the introduction of direct digital synthesis, it was within a digital computing environment that it first flourished as a practical means of producing dynamic spectra. Chowning’s description of FM [Chowning 1973], in fact using the theory of PM, led to its implementation in various computer music systems of the 70s (MUSIC 5, MUSIC 10, MUSIC 11, to cite but a few), and most notably in some of the first dedicated digital hardware synthesisers, such as the New England Digital Synclavier, and the Yamaha DX instrument line (who patented their version of PM based on Chowning’s method). An important aspect of any digital implementation of FM/PM is the fact that the method does not produce bandlimited spectra in theory, although in practice higher-order sidebands are have very little energy. Therefore, it is important to be mindful of this and control the modulation in such a way that any significant partials are contained within the digital baseband. This means that we should set our sampling rate to provide a reasonable value for the Nyquist frequency, which defines the limits of the baseband. The typical sampling rate of 44.1 kHz should be sufficient in most cases (the original DX7 ran at 49 kHz), but if there is enough computing resources to set this at higher values, we should avail of it. With certain hardware such as field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), it is possible to use sampling rates in the MHz range, in which case for all practical purposes we may consider the synthesis process directly in terms of its non-bandlimited continuous-time equations.

2.1. Implementation

In systems where oscillators are readily available as black boxes (e.g. in Csound, as op-codes), FM is generally the most straightforward form to be implemented. Although this poses issues for further extensions using higher order modulation or feedback topologies, it is perfectly applicable to simple carrier-modulator arrangements. When implementing these techniques from first principles, however, it may be more advisable to opt for the PM form, as it allows a far more flexible approach, and the possibility of further extensions. Given the interest, within the context of ubimus, on small computing devices, embedded systems, and do-it-yourself (DIY) hardware [Timoney et al. 2020], it is worth discussing the general lines of a PM implementation that may be deployed with such resources. This only requires a couple of components, which may be constructed in different ways depending on the capabilities of the hardware. The first one of these is the phase generator, which consists of a feedback arrangement taking the ratio of the fundamental frequency and the sampling rate as input, and producing a normalised phase signal in the range $[0 : 1)$. It requires one addition and a modulo operation, which in a system with a floating-point unit (FPU) can be implemented by taking the fractional part of the number. The flowchart for a phase generator is shown on Fig. 4. It is also possible to implement this component with integer mathematics, with a few modifications. The phase generator performs the integration needed to determine the instantaneous phase from a frequency input, and so it takes over the role of the integrator described in earlier examples.

Figure 4. A phase signal generator (left) and table lookup operator (right)

The other component is the waveshaper, which maps the phase to a given waveform (in the case of simple PM, to a sine or cosine wave). This is typically implemented using a function table lookup. One cycle of the waveform is pre-computed and stored in an array (the table) of a given size, and then looked up according to the phase signal. The table lookup operator flowchart is shown on Fig. 4. The normalised phase is scaled up to the table size L , and the modulo is applied. Note that if L is a power-of-two, then the wrap-around operation is simply to apply a bitmask $L - 1$ with a bitwise AND, which is fairly inexpensive. The wrapped-around phase is then used in the table lookup. Given the symmetries in a sinusoidal wave, it is often possible to save memory space (at the cost of a few operations) by storing one half or one quarter of the waveform. This was the strategy applied, for example, in the early DX synthesiser circuits, where PM was implemented with discrete logic components (instead of code running in a microprocessor). With these components in hand, it is fairly straightforward to implement digital PM synthesis (Fig. 5). In addition to the modulator and carrier, it is also common to provide envelopes for both the index of modulation z and the output amplitude. In fact, with the

addition of an envelope to control the signal amplitude, each oscillator, constituted by the phase and lookup components can be considered a separate unit called an *operator*, which may be combined in various ways with other similar components to extend the synthesis method into more complex configurations.

Figure 5. Digital PM synthesis

2.2. Complex Modulation

The first form of such extensions to simple FM/PM is to consider the use of a complex modulating wave, with more than one partial. It is important to note that the meaning of *complex* here has nothing to do with complex numbers, but it is used to mean a signal with more than one component, that is, not sinusoidal. A derivation of the complex modulation PM spectrum [LeBrun 1977] indicates that it is composed of partials at the sums and differences of the carrier and integer multiples of all modulation frequencies, $f_c \pm n_1 f_{m_1} \pm n_2 f_{m_2} \pm \dots \pm n_k f_{m_k}$, which can make it very dense if more than a few partials are present with significant energy in the modulator signal. One useful aspect of this arrangement is that only small indices of modulation z are needed for a sufficiently complex output, and for these values, the behaviour of the Bessel coefficients is more controlled (without the bipolar fluctuations seen with higher values of z). This produces much more smooth and natural spectral evolutions as the index of modulation is changed. In order to implement complex wave modulation, it is possible to take the two-modulator PM arrangement of Fig. 5 and add one or more further modulators, with their own individual z and f_m . Furthermore, if we consider an operator as described above, we can use two or more of these as modulators. We could go even further, and stack them to produce higher-order modulation arrangements, or use multiple carriers (Fig. 6). This is a very useful design, introduced in the DX series of synthesisers, which is only possible in such a straightforward way by the fact that we are implementing PM instead of FM.

2.3. Feedback

In fact, not only it is possible to combine operators to produce various topologies, we can also feed the output of an operator back to its input (Fig. 7), in this case with an additional envelope controlling the amount of feedback. For the system to be stable, we need to keep the index of modulation below or equal to unity. The carrier to modulator frequency ratio of course will be locked into a 1:1 relationship, and the resulting spectrum will have

Figure 6. A PM operator with envelope a , frequency f , and three different example topologies

a decaying curve, close to $\frac{1}{f}$, producing an output that is very similar to a sawtooth wave (with maximum modulation). There is an implicit one-sample delay between input and output as this is designed to be implemented within a digital environment.

Figure 7. A PM operator using feedback modulation

2.4. Complex Carriers

Using a complex carrier wave instead of a sinusoid is another possible variation on the simple PM arrangement. Note that this is different to using several separate sinusoidal carriers; the resulting spectra is different, even if we match each harmonic of the complex carrier with an oscillator at that frequency. The somewhat surprising result is that the higher partials of a waveform will receive more modulation relatively to the lower order harmonics. The modulation index acting on each component of the carrier is actually scaled by the harmonic number, and so we end up with a very rich spectrum, where aliasing may be an issue (depending of course on the sampling rate, carrier waveform, as well as the modulation index, f_c , and f_m). In any case, we can implement the modulation of any waveform by storing one period of it in a function table and then using table lookup as before.

2.5. Delay-line PM

Alternatively, we can dispense with the carrier wavetable and replace it by a variable delay line [Lazzarini et al. 2008a]. In this case, the phase modulation signal is applied to the delay time. Since this is positive-only (a negative delay implies being able to predict the future!), the modulation signal needs to be given a DC offset. In that case, it makes

the delay time vary from a minimum (near zero, but taking account of interpolation may require it to be one or two samples) to maximum of perhaps only a few milliseconds. The carrier signal can be any arbitrary input, which is placed in the delay line, and the same principles outlined above for a complex carrier PM may be applied. If we can estimate the fundamental frequency of the input, then it is possible to set a given $f_c : f_m$ ratio to produce different types of harmonic and inharmonic spectra. This method is also known as *adaptive* FM (although PM is actually employed).

2.6. Splitting Sidebands

If we return to the generalised modulation arrangement shown in the flowchart of Fig. 2, then it is possible to split the spectrum into even and odd sidebands by taking the product of two separate real-valued waveshapers (driven by a cosine and a sine waveforms) and a sinusoidal modulator. Furthermore if we employ analytic signals, then we can split these two outputs once more into upper and lower sidebands. This is called split-sideband synthesis (SpSB) [Lazzarini et al. 2008b], which is an extended form of phase modulation. In order to produce the four outputs, we need to combine the two waveshapers, their Hilbert transforms (which shift their phases by $\pi/2$), and an analytic sinusoid modulator (effectively a cosine and a sine pair of signals) in a matrix product. The Hilbert transforms can be computed using an allpass filter (which shifts the phase but does not affect the amplitude signal). The flowchart in Fig. 8 shows the complete structure for SpSB, with the H boxes denoting the $\pi/2$ phase delay produced by a Hilbert transform operator. The four output signals then can be recombined or spatialised as desired. This approach provides another timbral dimension to PM synthesis, beyond the simple manipulation of z and $f_c : f_m$.

Figure 8. SpSB synthesis flowchart

2.7. Modified FM

We can also modify the PM equation so that it takes in a purely imaginary index of modulation, giving rise to Modified FM synthesis (ModFM) [Lazzarini and Timoney 2010]. In this case the spectrum amplitudes are similar to PM, but defined instead by a set of scaled modified Bessel coefficients. ModFM is implemented via the ring modulation of a

sinusoid mapped by an exponential waveshaper and a sinusoidal carrier (obtained by modifying the PM arrangement of 2, middle, so that it uses only real signals). An extended form of ModFM can be designed by combining it with the original PM arrangement, and defining two new parameters to control the transition between the different states of the synthesis, as shown in Fig. 9. The interesting aspect of this is that, with certain combinations of these two parameters, it is possible to create single-sided spectra (either lower or upper), which are not scaled by Bessel coefficients (but follow another expression based on the modulation index). This allows for various other timbral transitions that are beyond the typical PM spectra.

Figure 9. Extended ModFM synthesis

3. Analogue Computing Environments

Modulation synthesis within an analogue computing environment has a number of differences to the digital implementations discussed above. Two of them are fundamental: (a) signals are continuous in time and amplitude; and (b) precision is dependent on circuit design and electronic component characteristics and tolerances. The first of these points exempts us from worrying about aliasing: within an analogue environment, there are no absolute theoretical frequency limits. The second tells us that achieving the type of precision warranted by a digital environment may be hard. We should also bear in mind the fundamentally different characteristics of an analogue programming environment. Instead of a set of stored instructions which are executed step-by-step, a program is a circuit patch, an *analogue* of the problem we want to simulate [Lazzarini and Timoney 2020]. The programming environment is typically given by a modular synthesis system with several units (oscillators, amplifiers, envelope generators, etc), and we are dependent on what these may offer in terms of signals and control. Of course, a bespoke circuit may be designed for a particular application (and such approach is fairly common in DIY/maker communities). Another possibility is the use of programmable analogue circuits, which have been introduced in recent years [Lazzarini and Timoney 2020]. Within an analogue audio computing, signals are usually carried by varying voltages. Such signals may be

unipolar (non-negative) only or bipolar; generally the former is reserved only for controls, whereas the latter can be used to carry either audio or control information. Module parameter voltages may be set by potentiometers, by control signals, or a combination of both. It is far less common to see the use of varying electric currents as a means of passing signals, even though internally, in the circuitry of synthesiser modules these are important but not normally exposed by their interfaces.

3.1. Implementation

As we noted before, the basic component used in FM is the oscillator, and this is applicable to both digital and analogue systems. Within a modular environment, the voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO) is the module that normally implements the generation of waveforms which are employed in modulation synthesis. In these, voltages can be used to control the fundamental frequency of a carrier signal, and their output can be used as a modulation source. They typically generate the classic waveforms defined by the sawtooth, pulse/square, and triangle shapes, as well as sinusoidal waves. We can delineate a VCO from fundamental building blocks. The first aspect we need to note is the form in which the voltage control is given to (or taken by) a VCO for its fundamental frequency. While in a digital environment, we just present the frequency in Hz, here we need to define what voltage represents a given frequency. There are two basic options: a linear map, where we apply a given voltage level directly to a frequency in Hz; and an exponential, where changes in voltages are proportional to an interval, typically 1V representing an octave interval (a frequency ratio of 1 : 2). This latter is far more common, and in many ways more reasonable, and so we should adopt it as the standard approach. This gives us the first requirement for a VCO circuit, an *exponential converter*, which will take a linear input in the form of a voltage level V , and convert it to an output frequency, $2^V f_r$, where f_r is an arbitrary frequency reference (defining the lower point of the scale). Exponential converters can be constructed using semiconductor technology, namely transistors, which give an exponential response in current to changes in input voltages [Chamberlin 1985, 184]. The oscillator proper then is composed of the two basic elements we have seen before, an integrator (with a reset circuit) and one or more waveshapers. The role of the integrator is produce a varying phase, as we saw in digital synthesis program, which is a ramp or a unipolar sawtooth wave. This is a periodically repeating signal with the frequency defined by its input voltage. The actual operation of an analogue integrator is fairly straightforward; if implemented using an operational amplifier [Lazzarini and Timoney 2020], it can be simply described by an inverting amplifier to which a loop including a capacitor is added (Fig. 10). This circuit will integrate any voltages presented at its input up to the saturation voltage limit of the operational amplifier. The slope of the voltage change, and therefore the time that it takes to reach saturation, is proportional to the input voltage.

Figure 10. A typical inverting op amp voltage integrator.

In order to produce a repeating waveform, we need a reset circuit which can discharge the capacitor so that the voltage can rise again at the output. This is equivalent to the modulo operation employed in the digital oscillator. The reset circuit can be implemented by a timer integrated circuit (IC) which fires a pulse that can close a switch to discharge the oscillator. Alternatively, we can use a comparator, for example in the form of a Schmitt trigger, which will fire once the waveform crosses a certain threshold. The reset in fact can take the form of a square wave signal, which when integrated produces a triangular output. In this case we have a *triangle core* oscillator. The ramp integrator output, however, yields a *sawtooth core* oscillator which uses a pulse as a reset signal [Chamberlin 1985, 183]. A waveshaper is then used to produce the final waveform signals. Starting with a sawtooth phase signal, we can apply a DC blocker in the form of a resistor-capacitor circuit (also called an AC coupler) to produce a bipolar output. From this sawtooth, employing full-wave rectification, where the negative voltage is mirrored as a positive value, we can obtain a triangle signal. From the phase input, using a comparator we can produce a pulse wave signal with variable width (or duty cycle; a square wave being represented by a 50% duty pulse). Finally, using a more complicated waveshaper we can shape a sinusoidal signal to various levels of precision or purity. A general schematic of the standard VCO is shown in Fig. 11

Figure 11. A standard VCO with sawtooth, triangle, and pulse waveform outputs

With regards to modulation synthesis, there are two aspects that are important to note about a standard VCO: (a) It takes in a frequency input, so FM, not PM is available; (b) The frequency input is exponential. Therefore, with a standard VCO neither PM nor FM in the form that we have so far seen can be implemented. For the former, we would need access to the integrator output, so that the signal at that point could be modulated. While this is not offered in the typical VCO, there are specialist modules that provide a means to do PM in this form, with voltage access to the circuitry after the integration point. In order to implement FM as it is done in a digital environment, we would need a linear (Hz/V) input that is added to voltage applied to the integrator (or another modification to the circuit with similar effect). That is more commonly offered by enhanced forms of VCO. Moreover, for FM to be properly implemented such modules need to allow bipolar signals to be fed to the integrator, as per the FM synthesis equation. Without these, some sort of misshapen frequency modulation signal is employed, with less well-defined results. For a proper FM implementation, the VCO requires a *through-zero* operation, that is, it can work in reverse phase [Hutchins 1981].

3.2. Exponential FM

Exponential FM (xFM) is therefore the typical mode of operation in an analogue environment with standard VCOs, and is generally contrasted with the additive form of FM

(which is referred to as *linear* FM). In xFM, since voltage signals are put through an exponential converter, the result is that any input modulation is multiplied by, rather than added to, the VCO frequency. Also, the current or voltage feeding the oscillator core is never going to be negative in this case. If compared to linear FM, this is equivalent to a distortion of the modulation waveform, as the signal is effectively passing through an exponential waveshaper. If a cosine wave is applied, then the resulting modulation is similar to that observed in ModFM, with modified Bessel coefficients defining the amplitude of the various partials of the waveform [Hutchins 1975]. One of the difficulties of xFM is that the modulation signal will most likely have some amount of energy at DC, which is going to be proportional to the Bessel coefficient of order zero (as a function of the modulation index). In this case then, changes in modulation amount would lead to an upwards pitch glide, since the modulation signal is applied to the frequency of the VCO. In fact, this is a general (less desirable) characteristic of FM versus PM, in that any DC component in the modulation wave will cause the carrier frequency to drift as opposed to just causing a phase offset in the waveform. So, while various inharmonic and even harmonic spectra may be tuned in with specific parameters of xFM (z, f_c, f_m), dynamic modification of spectra always has the subsidiary effect of a carrier frequency glide. This may or may not be an issue, depending on the musical application.

3.3. Stacked FM

As we saw earlier, within a digital environment, higher-order modulation may be successfully accomplished by stacked PM operators, producing a generally well-defined and predictable output spectrum. Since FM is the usual method employed in analogue systems, we may wonder whether some equivalent form of stacked modulation is possible, using a linear form of the method. The short answer is yes, but there are some complications due to the fact that DC components in a modulating signal are problematic. So, if we are considering simply a second-order (linear) FM arrangement, where we have two stacked modulators, it is possible to determine parameters that will not lead to the presence of 0 Hz partials in the modulator. For example, while a m ratio of $f_c : f_m = 1$ will lead to a DC component (by the virtue of the first lower sideband frequency being $f_c - f_m = 0$), an arrangement employing $f_c : f_m = 1 : 2$ will be guaranteed not to produce a 0 Hz partial. Alternatively, it is also possible to ensure that the modulation applied is mathematically equivalent to PM, leading theoretically to nothing but phase shifts, but this would require a more complex implementation. In any case, with simple or stacked FM implementation it is always important that we observe that the modulation signals have no DC applied to them at any stage of the circuitry, as otherwise we would not be able to dynamically control the modulation amount without the subsidiary effect of frequency glides.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we offered a survey of the various traditional and more modern formulations of phase and frequency modulation. We have also looked at their deployment in digital and analogue computing environments, noting the specific aspects and conditions of each. In particular, we saw that PM is more suitable than FM in terms of generality of implementation, particularly within a digital environment, while FM is more common in analogue systems. The rationale behind is that it is much more flexible to modify the phase of a carrier without having to take account for the integration step built into an

oscillator. This allows for stacking and feedback to be arranged more freely. While this should also be the case in analogue computing, it is far less common to find oscillator circuits that allow phase to be modified directly. We also noted that the modulation methods discussed here are particularly suited to limited computing resources, as they are very economical. Nevertheless, they can also benefit from devices that support extremely high sampling rates, as in this case their results can be derived directly from the continuous time equations that define them, without concern for aliasing distortion.

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